

Complexes of a Schiff Base, 2,3-Diphenyl-1,4-bis-(3'-methyl-5'-mercapto-1',2',4'-triazole)-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene with Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

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Metal complexes of the type $[M(DBTDB)(H_2O)_2]$, where DBTDB = a Schiff base 2,3-diphenyl-1,4-bis(3'-methyl-5'-mercapto-1',2',4'-triazole)-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene (derived from 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and benzil) and $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} , have been synthesised and characterised. The electronic spectra of the complexes suggest an approximately octahedral environment around the metal ions. All the complexes show normal magnetic moment values at room temperature. Infrared spectra indicates the coordination of the ligand through mercapto sulphur and exocyclic azomethine nitrogen. The Cu^{II} complex exhibit maximum fungitoxicity.

Mercapto derivatives of triazoles possess various biological activities¹. 3-Methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole has been used as an analytical reagent². It also forms stable metal complexes due to its chelating ability. As a part of our series of investigation³ with such ligand systems we describe here the synthesis and characterisation of a series of metal complexes with a new tetradentate SNNS-donor Schiff base derived from 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and benzil. These complexes are expected to possess antifungal activity.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are crystalline having high melting points and insoluble in common organic solvents. Freshly prepared complexes are feebly soluble in solvents having high dielectric constant values. They are decomposed in dilute acids and alkalies to form their corresponding sulphides indicating the presence of M-S bonding in the complexes⁴.

Ir spectra : Since the ligand molecule (DBTDB) is expected to contain a thioamide linkage, it

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, m.p.°C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	S	M
$(C_{20}H_{20}N_8O_2S_2)Cu$ (White, > 250)	45.0 (45.15)	3.6 (3.76)	21.1 (21.07)	12.1 (12.04)	11.7 (11.94)
$(C_{20}H_{20}N_8O_2S_2)Ni$ (Blue, > 250)	45.2 (45.56)	3.5 (3.79)	21.2 (21.26)	12.1 (12.15)	11.2 (11.14)
$(C_{20}H_{20}N_8O_2S_2)Co$ (Light grey, > 250)	45.1 (45.54)	3.9 (3.79)	21.1 (21.25)	12.2 (12.14)	11.1 (11.19)
$(C_{20}H_{20}N_8O_2S_2)Mn$ (White, > 250)	45.6 (45.88)	3.6 (3.82)	21.2 (21.41)	12.1 (12.23)	10.4 (10.51)
$C_{20}H_{18}N_8S_2$ (White, > 210)	55.0 (55.29)	4.2 (4.14)	25.5 (25.8)	15.0 (14.74)	—

may undergo thioketo-enol tautomerism. Two weak bands in the ir spectra of the ligand at ~ 2530 (SH) and ~ 745 cm^{-1} (C=S) confirm the existence of tautomeric forms. In addition, the ligand displays a broad band at $3050-3250$ cm^{-1} assigned to the combined antisymmetric and symmetric vibration of NH group. The broadness of the band is probably due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Further, the band at ~ 1620

cm^{-1} is assigned to the exocyclic azomethine $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. The bands of medium intensity at ~ 1575 (C=N) and 1040 cm^{-1} (N-N) (cyclic) are due to the triazole ring⁵. These are more or less in agreement with the spectrum of the 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole⁶. The band of medium intensity at ~ 2925 cm^{-1} is assigned to the phenyl ring vibration.

Upon complexation, the ligand bands undergo drastic change. The ir spectra of the complexes show a strong and broad band at $3450\text{--}3200$ cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ν_{OH} of the water molecules, which is further supported by another band at ~ 830 cm^{-1} characteristic of wagging mode of vibration of coordinated water molecules⁷. The far-ir spectra reveal the presence of a band of medium intensity at ~ 525 cm^{-1} (M-O) supporting the coordinating nature of the water molecules. The absence of the ligand band ~ 2530 cm^{-1} (S-H) in the complexes indicates that deprotonation has taken place at S-H group resulting in the formation of M-S bond. The disappearance of $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ band at ~ 745 cm^{-1} and appearance of a new band at ~ 770 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$, support the coordination of the mercaptosulphur to the metal centre. A very weak band of low intensity at ~ 420 due to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ also provides evidence for the formation of M-S bond².

The ligand band due to exocyclic $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ at ~ 1620 cm^{-1} undergoes a bathochromic shift and appears at 1610 cm^{-1} , suggesting the coordination of exocyclic azomethine nitrogen. The other ligand bands due to 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole remain unaffected in the complexes⁸.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties : The cobalt(II) complex possesses magnetic moment value of 3.94 B.M. at room temperature. The electronic spectra of the complex show bands at ~ 11600 and 15100 cm^{-1} , assigned to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, which arises due to ligand field transition of the octahedral component of the cobalt(II) complex. Another band observed at ~ 25200 cm^{-1} may be due to charge transfer.

The visible spectrum of the nickel(II) complex has the characteristic of 3A_2 ground state and shows a broad band with a centre at ~ 16200 cm^{-1} and another strong band at ~ 27800 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, in approximately octahedral field⁹. The magnetic moment value (2.80 B.M.) is slightly lower than the spin-only value, which can be attributed to partial quenching of the orbital motion and appreciable orbital over-lapping.

The copper(II) complex shows normal magnetic moment value (1.74 B.M.) at room temperature which is the expected value for a d^9 system. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows a broad band centred at ~ 16500 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ in an approximately octahedral environment. The width and symmetry of the band suggest strong Jahn-Teller distortion.

The electronic spectrum of the manganese(II) complex exhibits sharp bands at 18150 , 25000 and 28750 cm^{-1} corresponding to multiplicity forbidden transitions ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g + {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ respectively^{9,10}.

Thermal analyses : The thermograms of all the complexes show nearly the same pattern of decomposition leading us to believe that the complexes are isostructural. Most of them lose weight at $\sim 170^\circ$ in a single step with an exothermic peak. The weight-loss corresponds to the loss of two water molecules. The exothermic peak in the DTA curve suggests bond-breaking. These are characteristics of coordinated water molecules. Simultaneous elimination of two molecules of water at the same temperature may be due to their presence in the same chemical environment¹¹. The ligand moiety starts decomposing slowly above 200° , finally leaving behind the corresponding metal oxide around 850° . The weight-loss agrees with the suggested stoichiometry. The thermal stability of the complexes follows the order : $\text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{Mn}$.

Considering the planar structure of the ligand,

it is opined that the ligand (DBTDB) behaves as a tetradentate ligand coordinating through both mercapto-sulphur and exocyclic azomethine nitrogen.

Fungicidal activity : Thiourea and compounds containing thiourea residue exhibit fungitoxicity. It has been observed that their fungitoxicity is enhanced when a metal ion is incorporated into the thiourea moiety. The present complexes do have a thiourea residue. We thought it worthwhile to carry out fungicidal screening of the metal complexes.

The ligand as well as the complexes were tested against *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* by adopting Horsfall method¹². The evaluation was carried out at 1000 ppm in dioxane. The amount of germination or growth inhibition was determined after inoculation of the fungal spores to Czapekdox agar media and also to the media containing the test sample and keeping in an incubator for 5 days and the percentage of inhibition was calculated.

Copper chloride and cobalt chloride when used as fungicide cause damage to leaves¹³. However, the coordination compounds do little damage. The present investigation reveals that the copper(II) complex is considerably more fungitoxic than the cobalt(II), nickel(II) and manganese(II) complexes. The fungitoxicity of the complexes has been attributed to the presence of N-C-S linkage¹⁴.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck make. Solvents were used as such.

3-Methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole was prepared according to the reported method^{6,15}. The Schiff base DBTDB was prepared by dissolving 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and benzil in 2:1 molar ratio in warm ethanol and refluxing the mixture for 3 h. White crystals which were formed on cooling were washed with cold ethanol and dried over fused calcium chloride, (70%), m.p. 210°.

The complexes were prepared by adopting two different methods. In one of the methods, the complexes were prepared by direct reaction of the Schiff base with metal(II) salts whereas the second method involves the template process. However, complexes of the same stoichiometry were isolated in both the cases.

In a typical reaction, 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (2 mmol), benzil (1 mmol) were taken in ethanolic medium and refluxed for about 30 minutes. A solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O (1 mmol) in ethanol was added to it when a clear solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and ether and dried over fused calcium chloride. Other complexes were prepared in an identical manner by taking appropriate metal salts.

Metal and sulphur contents of the complexes were determined by adopting standard methods¹⁶. C, H and N were estimated by a MLW-CHN microanalyser. Ir spectra (KBr) and reflectance spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 and Cary 2930 spectrometers respectively. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. Thermal analyses were carried out on a Netzsch-429 automatic thermoanalyser by heating the complexes (50–100 mg) in air at rate of 10° min⁻¹. The molecular weight was determined by Rast's method.

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